

Minimum Cost Planning Strategies for Training Army Cadets Using Mixed Integer Programming Model

¹Abdullahi, N, ²Aliyu, Z.H., ³Sama'ila, I., ⁴Koko. K.M., and ⁵Dari, S.

^{1,2,3} Department of Mathematical Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA) Kaduna

⁴Department of Mathematics, Air force Institute of Technology, (AFIT) Kaduna

⁵Department of Mathematical Sciences, Kaduna State University, Kaduna

Corresponding Author e-mail: nabdullahi@nda.edu.ng, 08035587641

Abstract

This article, is adopted from the original paper of (Murty *et al*, 1995) as a non-mechanized mixed training model for the Direct Short Service Course (DSC) of the Nigerian Defence Academy. When the proficiency standards are given, the model will determine the training modes with the associated critical mission tasks, the resources needed, the training methods for using them, and the frequency with which each method needs to be repeated, in order to maintain the standards at minimum costs. A formulation and computation of the expected proficiency retention function, $PR_{tm}(r)$ (which is the expectation over discrete training schedule-time using triangular distribution), the Zero Practice Minimum, ZPM , the upper bound on the number of repetitions of training mode, u_{tm} , average slope of the learning curve for task-mode pair, a_{tm} , in the range of interest $0 \leq r \leq u_{tm}$, where r is the number of repetitions of training mode and the linear form of $PR_{tm}(r)$, $LPR_{tm}(r)$. The model is applied specifically to the analysis of training scenarios in a battalion training strategy of the Short Service wing of the Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna. The “Algebraic Mathematical Programming Language (AMPL)” a modeling language for mathematical programming was used to modeled the problem and solved using CPLEX 12.0. From the analysis of the model, a saving of about 10% was reported.

Keywords: MILP (Mixed integer linear programming), Military training, Resource allocation, Decision making, Triangular distribution.

1. Introduction

Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) is a variant of Integer Linear Programming (ILP) which is a technique of Linear Programming (LP), where some of the variables are required to be integral. This technique has been successfully used to solve a variety of problems in applications such as job scheduling, flow shop sequencing, capital budgeting, computer channel balancing, travelling sale man problem, telecommunications paths assignments, networks design, assignment of fleet to flight schedule, Agriculture, the military and so on. A collection of successful applications of IP is described by Badiru and Thomas (2009).

The conventional methods for solving MIP include the branch and bound (B&B), cutting plane, interior point method, group theoretic method, langrangian relaxation, neural network method, and constraint programming. The B&B algorithm is an enumerative approach, and is the most widely used approach for solving pure and MIP models, but it is well known that this algorithm suffers computational time difficulties and round off errors. Ramirez-Beltran (1995) and Lin et al (1992) suggested an algorithm that uses a neural network to direct the branching and consequently the B&B algorithm becomes more efficient. It is often very difficult to complete a tree search in a problem with over 100 integer variables, unless the formulation of the models involved variables in the constraints at lower bounds in case of MIP problems, and some special structure in case of pure IP, see Lee and Mitchell (1997).

Due to the versatility of IP model, many non- LP problems can be modeled as mixed integer problems, in this case a piecewise linear approximation to a non-linear function is being formulated. A simple example of this transformation is the “training mix model” where the expected proficiency (proficiency by definition is the state of performing a given task with a view to overcome difficulties) retention function (which is non-linear) was approximated by a linear function called a linear expected proficiency retention. Murty *et al* (1995).

Some recent improvements in solving an IPP have been pointed out by Abdullahi (2006). Those improvements can be summarized as follows, (1) The idea of using B&B with LP relaxation has not changed, however, the improved LP technology has had a major impact since for each node of the B&B tree, an LP is solved. (2) preprocessing can be used to make a hard IPP much easier to solve. Preprocessing refers to improving the initial formulation by eliminating redundancies, fixing variables, tightening constraints and generating new inequalities from logical relations among the variables. (3) Branch and cut (BC) and / or price (BP) is the third improvement and refers to adding additional strong constraints and /or columns to the problem to eliminate fractional solution during the B&B phase of the algorithm. (4) Interior point methods with B&C is the fourth improvement where the algorithm search for the optimal solution from the interior part of the feasible region of the solution space as well as combining it with B&C.

The paper by Griggs *et al* (1997), describes the development of an air mission planning algorithm for the joint stochastic warfare analysis research (JSTOCHWAR). The central objective of their work was to develop an algorithm to handle major factors bearing on the combat mission planning problem that provide look-ups for the JSTOCHWAR architecture, by using a mixed integer program (MIP) to allocate the optimum number and type of air craft and munitions against each target, the planning algorithm supplies the optimum degree of force to achieved the campaign objectives.

Nemhauser, (1996) carry out a research on the applications of MIP to selected problems of the U.S Army. The research was to support the “Concept Analysis Agency”, CAA in the solution of large-scale mixed integer programming models. In the same vain, Yang and Ignizio (1987), developed

an algorithm for the scheduling of army battalion training exercises. The paper deals with a real world, massive scheduling problem that exists within the military sector. Specifically, it addresses the problem of the scheduling of training exercises, over a given planning horizon (usually, a year), for a number of army battalions at a given military base. As such, the problem is a massive, resource-constrained scheduling problem that is beyond the scope of more elegant, exact methods of operations research. To solve the problem, they developed a two-phase heuristic approach that not only provides results within a reasonable time, but also exhibits substantially improved schedules over those that had been derived manually, via the base scheduling office (an aspect that should serve as a warning to those who might advocate the use of expert systems). While the specific approach is addressed toward a very specific scenario, it is believed that the method should be extendable to other types of resource constrained scheduling problems.

Although, the Short Service Commission training and other levels of training in NDA are not fully mechanized, in this paper an analysis for a training exercise schedule for a cadets' battalion is presented. We adopt the notations and definitions presented in Murty *et al* (1995), since the model can be applied to any type of training (including non-mechanized) scenarios. The problem can be handled using MIP model and the LP relaxation (i.e. ignoring the integral restriction) of the MIP.

Due to the unique structure of the "army training mixed model" model, when the values of the integer variables are rounded up to the nearest integer values in the optimum solution of the LP relaxation, it yields a feasible solution for the MIP that is very close to the true integer optimum. This is in contrast to the general theory of IP, where the relaxed IP optimal solution is not necessarily feasible to the original IP when the values of the integer variables are rounded up to the nearest integer values. (Hillier & Lieberman, 1980).

2. Methodology (Derivations of inputs for the analytical model)

In this section we give a summary of how to derived the inputs needed for the analytical model. For a more details analysis, interested reader can see (Yang and Ignizio,1987, Murty *et al*,1995, Nemhauser,1996, Balakrishnan and Nevzorov, 2003 and Jaber, Kher and Davis, 2009).

Training cycle:

Training cycle is the period of six months (June to November) which is the planning horizon for training decisions.

Unit:

The unit is a battalion comprising of 138 army cadets whose training activities over the training cycle is being considered. The purpose of training is to attain proficiency on critical tasks which can be defined as those activities that are essential to the successful performance of unit's assigned mission.

Critical Mission Tasks (CMT's):

Tasks (classification of events into categories or priorities to be achieved) are classified by level into battalion, company, platoon and crew tasks, depending on the maneuvers during which training will be inculcated into the trainees. For example, if training is to be received for a task in

a maneuver involving a whole platoon, this task is classified as a platoon task, or if training is to be received for a task in a maneuver involving a whole company this task is classified as company task etc. A list of all the tasks for which training was received are specified and these tasks are called CMT's (Critical Mission Tasks). The set of CMT's is an essential input as each CMT leads to a constraint in the model.

Training Modes:

A training mode is an event or exercise (activity to be conducted) in which a whole unit (i.e a crew, platoon, company etc) will participate simultaneously, focusing on training for the accomplishments of a specific mission. During training, various participants may be engaged in a variety of activities which train them for a variety of CMTs. Thus training modes provide training for a subset of CMTs in the specified list. Training modes are classified into platoon training modes, crew training modes etc, depending on the level of unit for which they are designed. The model contains a decision variable for each mode which represents the frequency each cadet in the unit repeats that mode during the training cycle in order to achieve the proficiency on the CMT.

For each training mode in the list, the following data was given.

- ˆ (a). The subsets of CMTs for which this mode provides training
- (b) The device or simulator that this mode uses
- (c) The number of hours that one session of this mode takes
- (d) The operational costs associated with the mode.

Zero Practice Minimum (ZPM)

The proficiency or skill of a trained soldier for any task is expected to decay over time until he/she is trained by some means. After a training session, proficiency is expected to increase and then begin to decay again until more training is received. The transition of a proficiency from one state to another is characterized by the complexity of the task and its rate of decay, (Murty *et al*, 1995 and Jaber, Kher and Davis, 2009). Naturally, knowledge decreases or decays with time, if no training were received. The proficiency level of a well-trained soldier would decay to a base level which is called the ZPM for that task if no further training is received.

Training Effectiveness Data

Some training modes may be more effective in training a specific task than other modes. The effectiveness of each mode for each task is measured using a proficiency scale from 0 (no proficiency) to 1 (maximum proficiency). The analytical model uses as its input a standard proficiency level i.e. an acceptable or target level for each task on the zero to one (0 to 1) scale. This standard level may be different for different tasks. In this paper, the standard level was set as 0.7, for all the tasks.

The proficiency of a soldier for any task is expected to decay overtime until he/she is trained by some means. We defined *ZPM* as the base level in which proficiency level of a well-trained soldier would decay to. The *ZPM* is between 0 and 0.7. The *ZPM* value for each *CMT* is needed as input for the analytical model. The *ZPM* values for all the *CMTs* are usually evaluated using responses of subject matter experts. In Murty, *et al*, 1995 the procedures to determine skill decay overtime

was not given, and our investigation shows that the Nigerian Defence Academy has no any developed analytical procedures to determine skill decay overtime. Therefore, the *ZPM* was evaluated using responses of subject matter experts and the fact that decay is a random process; Smith (2005), hence this will give rise to an exponential decay with time. The decay of a particular state of proficiency is determine by the decay constant λ . The probability of a proficiency (or skill) decaying in a time interval $d\beta$ is $\lambda d\beta$. We assume the probability is the same for all proficiency in the same level or state.

Suppose we have $S_t(\beta)$ skill for a task ; t ; in a particular state at time β , then in a time interval $d\beta$ a number $S_t(\beta)\lambda d\beta$ will decay, so:

$$dS_t(\beta) = -\lambda S_t(\beta) d\beta \quad (1)$$

The minus sign indicate decrease in skill or proficiency; rearranging we have

$$\frac{dS_t(\beta)}{S_t(\beta)} = -\lambda d\beta \quad \text{solving for } S_t(\beta)$$

This give
$$S_t(\beta) = S_t(0)e^{-\lambda\beta} \quad (2)$$

A characteristic of this equation is that in a fixed time interval β , a fixed fraction $e^{-\lambda\beta}$ will decay. As mentioned earlier decay is a random process which can be modeled as a geometric process the rate of which is a constant, λ . The probability of a proficiency decaying in a time interval will be given by the inverse of the initial proficiency or skill at time $\beta = 0$ i.e. $\frac{1}{S_t(0)}$ (Jaber, Kher and Davis, 2009). This is to ensure that the decay is a decreasing function. This will be true however only if $S_t(0) < 1$, since $0 < S_t(0) < 1$, then the decay constant, λ , will be given by.

$$\lambda = \frac{0.01}{S_t(0)}$$

The *ZPM* in this case was computed using the relation

$$ZPM = S_t(0) \exp(0.01/ S_t(0)) \beta t \quad (3)$$

The constant $(0.01/ S_t(0))$ (decay rate constant) is consistent with the rate constant given in the learning curve of Figure (1) below which is asymptotic to 1.

Proficiency gain data for each pairs (t , m):

For a task t and a training mode m that trains t, defined

$PR_{tm}(r)$ = the expected proficiency retention by the end of the training period, as a function of r , the number of times mode m is repeated during the training period. Murty *et al* (1995).

The gain in proficiency from a training session is a function of both the task and the training mode used. The aim is to make sure that every soldier in the participating unit retains by the end of the cycle proficiency level \geq the standard level on every CMT. The proficiency level (of a well-trained soldier) retained by the end of a training cycle is expected to be a monotonic non-decreasing function of the number of times the mode is repeated during the cycle, ie.

$$PR_{tm}(1) \leq PR_{tm}(2) \leq PR_{tm}(3) \dots$$

On the other hand, training improves tasks proficiency less and less with each repetition of the training session so for $r \geq 1, PR_{tm}(r) - PR_{tm}(r - 1)$ is expected to be monotonic decreasing with r (property of concave function).

Due to the assumption of gradual decay of knowledge with time the proficiency retained by the end of the cycle, not only depends on r , but on the precise timing within the cycle when those training sessions were taken. However, soldiers are busy and when we require that they take a training session we cannot predict the exact point of time when that will occur. Hence the definition of $PR_{tm}(r)$ is for an average soldier, a statistical average base on the assumption that the r repetitions of mode m occur according to the triangular distribution, (Balakrisnan and Nevzorov, 2003) over the training cycle that favors more repetitions occurring closer to the end of to the cycle. If we plot $PR_{tm}(r)$ against r and join the consecutive points by a straight line segment, we get a piecewise linear curve called the learning curve, for the task-mode pair (t, m) figure (1) gives the curve of $PR_{tm}(r)$

Figure 1. Learning curve for (t, m) pairs where r , is the number of repetitions of mode m during training cycle.

The curve $PR_{tm}(r)$ is asymptote to $PR_{tm}(r) = 1$

The slope of the learning curve is expected to decrease as r increase, and hence it will be a piecewise – linear concave. The methodology for determining the learning curve for every task-mode pairs (t, m) such that mode m trains for task t , were given as follows:

Each task is broken down into its constituents’ subtasks and actions, and then collecting judgment of subject matter experts on the perceived capability of each training mode to train each of these subtasks and actions. The overall task-mode rating is computed by taking a weighted average of the subtasks and action rating. An exponential decay function with time is applied to these ratings and a statistical average obtained by taking an expectation over time; under the assumption of the triangular distribution for the time points at which training session are scheduled in the training cycle. Values of $PR_{tm}(r)$ have been estimated for every task-mode pair (t, m) such that m trains for t , using the above methodology, for all $r = 1$ to 10. Here 10 was found to be a practical upper bound on the number of times that a training mode could be repeated over the training cycle by a unit.

We used the following relationship to formulate the $PR_{tm}(r)$, thus for a task-mode pairs (t, m) , suppose wa_{tm} is the weighted average rating. Let the time taken for mode m to trains task, t , be, β_{tm} , then applying the exponential decay function with β_{tm} , we have the task-mode pair rating as:

$$\varphi(t, m) = wa_{tm} e^{-\left(\frac{0.01}{wa_{tm}}\right)\beta_{tm}} \quad (4)$$

A statistical average; $\theta(t, m)$; obtained by taking expectation overtime, β_m , (where β_m is the time points) in which training sessions are scheduled in the training cycle, according to the triangular distribution. $\theta(t, m)$ is computed as follows:

$$\theta(t, m) = \varphi(t, m) \int_0^r \beta_m \left(\left(2 - \frac{\beta_m}{1440}\right) / 1440 \right) \times \left(\left(1 - \frac{u}{10}\right) / 10 \right) du$$

but β_m 's are time point, hence,

$$\theta(t, m) = \varphi(t, m) \beta_m \left(\left(2 - \frac{\beta_m}{1440}\right) / 1440 \right) \times \int_0^r 2 \left(\left(1 - \frac{u}{10}\right) / 10 \right) du \quad (5)$$

Hence the estimated gain in proficiency, $PR_{tm}(r)$ as a function of r , is given by

$$PR_{tm}(r) = \theta(t, m) + ZPM \quad (6)$$

Therefore when $r = 0$, equation (5) will be zero and hence $PR_{tm}(0) = ZPM$. Equation (6) gives the learning curve for each task – mode pairs (t, m) and is piecewise linear concave.

A linear approximation for the learning curve (being non-linear) is given below, and its justification in the context of the army’s problem. Originally task-mode pairs (t, m) (where m provide training for t) were classified into two categories as follows:

Class 1 task-mode pair

A task-mode pair (t, m) belongs to this class if $PR_{tm}(r)$ reaches or exceeds the standard level of proficiency for task t , for some number of repetitions $r \leq 10$ of this mode.

Class 2 task-mode pair

A task mode pair (t, m) belongs to this class if m trains for t but $PR_{tm}(10) <$ the standard level of proficiency for this task.

Linear approximation of the learning curve for a task-mode pair from class 1 (class 2)

For a task-mode pair (t, m) belonging to class 1 or class 2, defined

u_{tm} = smallest value of r for which $PR_{tm}(r) \geq$ standard level for task t , or

$u_{tm} = 8$, if the value of r beyond which the increase in expected proficiency retention is insignificant respectively.

In the case of class 2 we found out that for all task-mode pairs (t, m) the values of $PR_{tm}(r)$ taper off fairly quickly to some value strictly less than the standard level for this task as r increases. We noted that after $r = 8$, the increase in $PR_{tm}(r)$ with each additional repetition of this mode is negligible that is why u_{tm} was approximated to 8.

If training mode m is selected in the optimal set, since each repetition of it cost money for the sake of meeting the proficiency retention constraint on task t , there is no reason to repeat it more than u_{tm} times during the training cycle. This is the range of values of r , the number of repetitions of training mode m of interest for meeting the proficiency retention. The constraint on task t is $0 \leq r \leq u_{tm}$, in this case defined;

$$a_{tm} = \frac{PR_{tm}(u_{tm}) - PR_{tm}(0)}{u_{tm}} \tag{7}$$

as the average slope of the learning curve for (t, m) in the range of interest for r , and

$$LPR_{tm}(r) = PR_{tm}(0) + a_{tm}r \tag{8}$$

as the linear approximation for the expected proficiency retention for the task t when mode m is repeated r times.

For a task-mode pair (t, m) in class 1 or class 2, the proficiency retention estimates $PR_{tm}(r)$ was approximated by $LPR_{tm}(r)$, in constructing the analytical model for the problem. In fact this particular approximation (ie $LPR_{tm}(r)$) exemplified the fact that many non-linear problems such as $PR_{tm}(r)$ can be modeled as a MIP, this is one of the applications of combinatorial optimization, (Hoffman and Padberg, 2004).

The justification for this approximation were as follows. In the range of interest $0 \leq r \leq u_{tm}$, $PR_{tm}(r) \geq LPR_{tm}(r)$ since $PR_{tm}(r)$ is concave. Any error in the conclusions as a result of approximating the learning curve by the linearized $LPR_{tm}(r)$ is an error on the safe side as the army would prefer to have soldier trained to a slightly higher level than to see their capabilities fall below par. Also the upper bound u_{tm} that is placed on the decision variable x_{tm} in the model, prevent it from selecting values of x_{tm} at which $LPR_{tm}(r)$ is an over estimate of $PR_{tm}(r)$, (Murty *et al* ,1995).

For (t, m) belonging to class 1, in the range $r \geq u_{tm}$ both $PR_{tm}(r)$ and $LPR_{tm}(r)$ are \geq the standard level. So if an optimum number of replications of mode m is $> u_{tm}$ replacing $PR_{tm}(r)$ by $LPR_{tm}(r)$ would not affect the results of the model. In the model, the decision variable x_{tm} that select the number of repetitions, x_{tm} provides an upper bound for x_{tm} thereby restricting the number of repetitions. In constructing the training mix model therefore the proficiency retention estimates $PR_{tm}(r)$ were approximated by the values of $LPR_{tm}(r)$

Additivity assumption

Proficiency for a task can be acquired by training with any of the available training modes associated with it. The proficiency retention for a task is the sum of the proficiency retention values from the selected training modes, which trains this task. The assumption of additivity is equivalent to stating that the underlying mathematical model can be formulated in terms of linear relations, (Taha, 2003).

Since the slope of the learning curve decreases with an increasing r , b_t was defined as the minimal proficiency retention needed at the end of the training cycle in order to satisfy the proficiency constraint corresponding to t , and it is equal to the standard level minus the *ZPM* for *CMT*, t .

3. Formulation of Mathematical Model

In this section we will determine the sets, parameters, decision variables, constraints and objective function of the model:

Sets: $CMTs'$ be the set of “Critical Mission Tasks” considered, $t \in CMTs$

M the set of training modes considered, $m \in M$

Parameters: n = total number of personnel who need training

p_m = number of persons who participate simultaneously in each session of training mode $m \in M$

c_m = cost (sum of operational costs and the prorated equipment cost) per session of training mode $m \in M$

b_t = the minimal proficiency retention needed at the end of the training cycle in order to satisfy the proficiency constraint corresponding to $t \in CMT$,

$I_{tm} = 1$, if mode m provides some training for $t \in CMT$, 0, otherwise

u_{tm} = upper bound on the number of repetitions of mode m that count towards satisfying the proficiency retention constraint corresponding to $t \in CMT$ defined only if $I_{tm} = 1$

a_{tm} = average slope of the learning curve for the task mode pair (t, m) in the range of interest $0 \leq r \leq u_{tm}$ where r is the number of repetitions of mode m , defined only if $I_{tm} = 1$

Decision variables: x_{tm} = number of repetitions of mode m per cadet, that count towards satisfying proficiency constraint corresponding to $t \in CMT$, treated as a continuous variable; defined only for pairs (t, m) such that $I_{tm} = 1$

y_m = total number of repetitions of mode m per soldier, an integer variable.

Constraints: (i). minimal proficiency retention constraints needed at the end of the training cycle in order to satisfy the proficiency constraint corresponding to $t \in CMT$. Thus, for each t :

$$\sum_{m \text{ such that } I_{tm}=1} a_{tm}x_{tm} \geq b_t \text{ for each } t$$

(ii). variable upper bound constraints on the number of times a training mode m will train t that count toward satisfying the accepted (skill) proficiency level for all (t, m) pairs such that m trains t :

$$0 \leq x_{tm} \leq u_{tm} \text{ for all } (t, m) \text{ such that } I_{tm} = 1$$

(iii). variable lower bound constraints, which is the difference between the two decision variables, (see Murty *et al*, 1995).

The mixed integer programming, short service training model

Time Points for the analytical model.

We define and compute the various time constants used in the construction of the model as follows:

β_t - The total training time in hours for CMT, t , in the training cycle.

- β_{tm} - Average time taken by any training mode m to trains CMT, t
- β_m - Time points in which training sessions are scheduled in the training cycle for each task mode pair (t, m) .

From the training schedules, for β_t , we arrange all task-mode pair (t, m) such that, mode m trains task t . This methodology was used to calculate all β_t 's and β_{tm} 's for the remaining CMT 's. Then β_{tm} 's were generated from the assumption on training hour per day and the training schedule for the period of June to November.

Each task was broken down into its constituent subtasks and actions, we then collected judgments of subject matter experts on the perceived capability of each training modes to train each of these sub tasks and actions. The overall task-mode rating was computed by taking a – weighted average of the sub task(s) and actions rating. An exponential decay function with time (β_{tm}) is applied to the task – mode pair ratings (α_{tm}); and a statistical average obtained by taking expectation over time (β_m) under the assumption of the triangular distribution for the time points at which training sessions are scheduled in the training cycle.

From the definition of ZPM and $PR_{tm}(r)$ as given above, where ZPM is the decay base level of the proficiency of a well trained soldier when training is not received for CMT, t in the cycle; while $PR_{tm}(r)$ is the expected proficiency retention by the end of the training period as a function of r , the number of times mode m is repeated during the training period. The ZPM is between zero and the standard level (0 to 0.7). For each task-mode pair (t, m) , the value of $PR_{tm}(r)$ was estimated, and the training effectiveness data and data for the analytical model is given in appendix 1 and 2.

The remaining data to implement the model are = 138, which is the unit under consideration. Then P_m , the number of persons who participate simultaneously in each session of mode m , at platoon level is 12. While b_t , the minimal proficiency retention needed at the end of the training cycle in order to satisfy the proficiency constraint corresponding to CMT, t ; which is equal to the standard level minus the ZPM for that task. Lastly the total cost C_m in unit of 1000 naira, associated with the training modes: TEWT = 3.552, CIN = 83.334, COZ = 125, CFT = 215.625, CKR = 133.332 and CHD = 286.664. Thus we have:

$$\text{Minimize the total cost } z = \sum_{m=1}^6 \left(\frac{138}{12}\right) c_m y_m \quad (9)$$

$$\text{subject to } \sum_{m=1}^6 a_{tm} x_{tm} \geq b_t \text{ for each } t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 7 \quad (10)$$

such that $I_{tm}=1$

$$0 \leq x_{tm} \leq u_{tm} \text{ for all } (t, m) \text{ such that } I_{tm} = 1 \quad (11)$$

$$y_m - x_{tm} \geq 0 \text{ for all } (t, m) \text{ such that } I_{tm} = 1 \quad (12)$$

$$y_m \geq 0 \quad \text{integer for all } m = 1, 2, 3 \dots \dots 6 \quad (13)$$

$$x_{tm} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } (t, m) \text{ such that } I_{tm} = 1 \quad (14)$$

The difference between the two decision variables y_m and x_{tm} is given in (Murty *et al*, 1995). The values in appendix 2 with the total cost c_m are substituted in the above model (9 – 14) .The model was coded in AMPL, (Fourer, *et al*, 2003), and use IBM-CPLEX 12.5.0 solver, implemented on a HP corei³ processor 2.27 GHz 4 GB RAM PC and solved by CPLEX 12.5.0

4. Results and Discussion

The mixed integer programming, short service training model was solved. Table (1) and table (2) give the summary of the optimal feasible solution of the MIP and LR problem respectively. (Note that this is a summary of the solution due to confidentiality of the data obtained.

Table (1) MIP (SST) Optimal output summary

Variable	Optimal Values
Z	5968.362
y_1	3
y_3	3
y_5	1
x_{11}	0.056250
x_{21}	1.636364
x_{31}	0.750
x_{33}	2
x_{35}	1
x_{41}	2.444
x_{45}	1
x_{51}	1.60
x_{55}	1
x_{63}	2.444
x_{65}	1
x_{73}	2.875
x_{75}	1

Variables not listed are not basic at the optimal extreme point.

Table (2) LR (SST) optimal output Summary

Variable	Optimal Value
Z	5518.63915
y_1	1.6364
y_5	3.5556
x_{11}	0.020694
x_{15}	3.5556
x_{21}	1.6364
x_{35}	3.5556
x_{41}	1.6364
x_{45}	3.5556
x_{51}	1.6364
x_{55}	3.00
x_{61}	1.6364
x_{65}	3.5556
x_{75}	3.5556

Variables not listed are either not basic variables or zero at the optimal extreme point.

From the optimal solution on y_m , and the number of persons to be trained we compute the number of sessions per battalion for the two cases above and the result is given below.

Table (3) MIP Training mode summary for 6 months cycle.

Mode	Unit	No. of sessions per unit	No. of sessions per battalion
TEWT	Platoon	3	35
COZ	Platoon	3	35
CKR	Platoon	1	12
Total cost/6 months			N5.968 million

Approximate optimum from the lp relaxation

Consider the LP relaxation of the MIP (9 - 14) obtained by ignoring the integer restrictions on the decision variable y_m . Suppose $(\bar{x}_{tm}), (\bar{y}_m)$ (be an optimum solution of this LP as given in table (2)). We define

$\tilde{y} = \tilde{y}_m$, where $\tilde{y}_m = \lceil \bar{y}_m \rceil =$ ceiling of \bar{y}_m , ie the smallest integer $\geq \bar{y}_m$. It is reasonable to take \tilde{y} as an approximation to an optimum training mix, ie make each cadet take \tilde{y}_m session of each training mode m over the training cycle. The justification they give for this includes

1. From the structure of (9 - 14) it is clear that since \bar{y}_m is a feasible solution for it, so is (\tilde{y}_m) . From the definition of \tilde{y} above we see that, for each CMT, \tilde{y} has the same or higher expected proficiency retention by the end of the training cycle than \bar{y} , which meets the standard without being integral. Thus if there is any error in \tilde{y} , it is on the safer side of being slightly over the standard.
2. Another reason is that the model (9 - 14) try to strike a balance at the level of an average soldier.

Now from table (2) and the definition of \tilde{y} we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{y}_1 = 1.6364 & \Rightarrow \tilde{y}_1 = \lceil 1.6364 \rceil = 2 \\ \bar{y}_5 = 3.5556 & \Rightarrow \tilde{y}_5 = \lceil 3.5556 \rceil = 4 \end{aligned}$$

The integer solution, \tilde{y} , obtained by rounding the optimum solution \bar{y} of the LP relaxation for the problem given in (9 - 14) is:

Table (4) LP Approximate of training mode Summary for 6 months

Mode	Unit	No. Of sessions per unit	No. Of sessions per battalion
TEWT	Platoon	2	23
CKR	Platoon	4	46
Total cost / 6 months			N6.215 million

5. Conclusion

Even though the Short Service training is not a mechanized training strategy, the training mix model would contribute significantly to the improvement in the capabilities of the cadets training development by providing an analytical tool for the development and evaluation of current, new and proposed training systems. The model can be used to make informed decision on alternative training methods and to improve army training.

The model integrates military training concepts and mathematical programming into an innovative tool that will allow the NDA leadership to define clearly and decisively the cost and effectiveness tradeoff between different training methods. We conclude that since repetitions of the training modes (not in the optimum mix) cost money and are less effective compared with those in the optimum mix we felt the authority should consider a review of the existing training strategy. Our investigation shows that training modes in the NDA were designed based on the method of their execution and purpose, not on the main device the training modes use. This makes it difficult to

obtain summary on resources usage based on device used, the number of sessions required on each device and the number of devices needed will be difficult to compute.

Acknowledgment: This work was funded by Tetfund IBR allocation. The authors appreciate the agency for the opportunity.

Appendix (1) training effectiveness data

<i>CMT</i>	<i>t, m</i>	<i>a_{tm}</i>	<i>s_t</i>	<i>β_{tm}</i> (hrs)	<i>β_t</i> (hrs)	<i>β_m</i> (hrs)	<i>ZPM</i>
T01	t ₁ m ₁	0.75				912	0.25
T01	t ₁ m ₂	0.70				714	0.25
T01	t ₁ m ₃	0.72	0.174	13.24	79.43	956	0.25
T01	t ₁ m ₄	0.77				953.14	0.25
T01	t ₁ m ₅	0.70				1194	0.25
T01	t ₁ m ₆	0.80				1431.43	0.25
T02	t ₂ m ₁	0.78				942	0.52
T02	t ₂ m ₄	0.80	0.79	11.14	33.43	953.14	0.52
T02	t ₂ m ₆	0.80				1431.43	0.52
T03	t ₃ m ₁	0.68				936	0.33
T03	t ₃ m ₂	0.70				714	0.33
T03	t ₃ m ₃	0.75	0.72	9.24	55.43	956	0.33
T03	t ₃ m ₄	0.73				953.14	0.33
T03	t ₃ m ₅	0.78				1194	0.33
T03	t ₃ m ₆	0.68				1431.43	0.33
T04	t ₄ m ₁	0.75				936	0.37
T04	t ₄ m ₂	0.80				714	0.37
T04	t ₄ m ₃	0.70	0.77	9.24	55.43	956	0.37
T04	t ₄ m ₄	0.82				953.14	0.37
T04	t ₄ m ₅	0.75				1194	0.37
T04	t ₄ m ₆	0.80				1431.43	0.37
T05	t ₅ m ₁	0.75				942	0.42
T05	t ₅ m ₂	0.80				714	0.42
T05	t ₅ m ₃	0.70	0.79	8.24	49.43	956	0.42
T05	t ₅ m ₄	0.83				953.14	0.42
T05	t ₅ m ₅	0.80				1194	0.42
T05	t ₅ m ₆	0.82				1431.33	0.42
T06	t ₆ m ₁	0.73				936	0.36
T06	t ₆ m ₂	0.78				714	0.36
T06	t ₆ m ₃	0.68	0.75	9.24	55.43	956	0.36
T06	t ₆ m ₄	0.73				953.14	0.36
T06	t ₆ m ₅	0.80				1194	0.36
T06	t ₆ m ₆	0.78				1431.43	0.36
T07	t ₇ m ₂	0.45				714	0.38
T07	t ₇ m ₃	0.63				956	0.38

T07	t_7m_4	0.65	0.63	6.3	31.43	953.14	0.38
T07	t_7m_5	0.63				1194	0.38
T07	t_7m_6	0.78				1431.43	0.38

Appendix (2) Data for the Analytical model

CMT, t	M	t, m	ZPM	C	u_{tm}	a_{tm}
T01	TEWT	t_1m_1	0.25	1	6.00	0.08
T01	CIN	t_1m_2	0.25	2	8.00	0.05
T01	COZ	t_1m_3	0.25	1	6.00	0.08
T01	CFT	t_1m_4	0.25	1	6.00	0.08
T01	CKR	t_1m_5	0.25	1	6.00	0.08
T01	CHD	t_1m_6	0.25	1	5.00	0.10
T02	TEWT	t_2m_1	0.52	1	2.00	0.11
T02	CFT	t_2m_4	0.52	1	2.00	0.11
T02	CHD	t_2m_6	0.52	1	2.00	0.13
T03	TEWT	t_3m_1	0.33	1	5.00	0.08
T03	CIN	t_3m_2	0.33	1	6.00	0.06
T03	COZ	t_3m_3	0.33	1	4.00	0.10
T03	CFT	t_3m_4	0.33	1	5.00	0.09
T03	CKR	t_3m_5	0.33	1	4.00	0.11
T03	CHD	t_3m_6	0.33	1	4.00	0.09
T04	TEWT	t_4m_1	0.37	1	4.00	0.09
T04	CIN	t_4m_2	0.37	1	4.00	0.09
T04	COZ	t_4m_3	0.37	1	4.00	0.09
T04	CFT	t_4m_4	0.37	1	3.00	0.11
T04	CKR	t_4m_5	0.37	1	3.00	0.11
T04	CHD	t_4m_6	0.37	1	3.00	0.12
T05	TEWT	t_5m_1	0.42	1	3.00	0.10
T05	CIN	t_5m_2	0.42	1	3.00	0.09
T05	COZ	t_5m_3	0.42	1	4.00	0.08
T05	CFT	t_5m_4	0.42	1	3.00	0.11
T05	CKR	t_5m_5	0.42	1	3.00	0.12
T05	CHD	t_5m_6	0.42	1	3.00	0.12
T06	TEWT	t_6m_1	0.36	1	5.00	0.08
T06	CIN	t_6m_2	0.36	1	5.00	0.08
T06	COZ	t_6m_3	0.36	1	4.00	0.09
T06	CFT	t_6m_4	0.36	1	5.00	0.08
T06	CKR	t_6m_5	0.36	1	3.00	0.12
T06	CHD	t_6m_6	0.36	1	3.00	0.12
T07	CIN	t_7m_2	0.38	2	8.00	0.04
T07	COZ	t_7m_3	0.38	1	4.00	0.08
T07	CFT	t_7m_4	0.38	1	4.00	0.09
T07	CKR	t_7m_5	0.38	1	4.00	0.09
T07	CHD	t_7m_6	0.38	1	3.00	0.12

$t = CMT, m = \text{training mode}, ZPM \text{ is for } t, c = \text{class of } (t, m).$

References

- Abdullahi, N. (2006). Adopting a linear programming model in military training: A case study of the U.S Army "Training mix model" in the Nigerian Defence Academy Kaduna. Unpublished MSc Thesis in Mathematics, Department of Mathematics, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria .
- Badiru, A., B., and Thomas, M.,U., 2009, Handbook of military industrial engineering (Industrial innovation series), CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, 6000 Broken Sound Parkway NW.
- Balakrishnan, N., and Nevzorov, V.B., "A Primer on Statistical Distributions", 2003 John Wiley & Sons, Inc. NY
- Fourer, R., Gay, D., and Kernighan, B.W., "AMPL: A modeling language for mathematical programming" 2nd Eds (2003) brookes/Cole.
- Jaber, M.Y., Kher, H.V., and Davis, D.J., Countering forgetting through training and deployment, in Handbook of Military Industrial Engineering, (Eds), Badiru and Thomas, 2009, CRC Press, New York
- Griggs, B.J.; Parnell, G. G. S and Lehmkuhl, L. J. (1997); "An air mission planning algorithm using decision analysis and mixed integer programming," Operations Research, vol. 45, pp. 662–676,
- Hillier, F.S. & Lieberman, G.J. (1980). Introduction to Operations Research (3rd edition) Holden – Day Corporation, San Francisco.
- Hoffman, K.L. & Padberg, M. (1991). Improving the LP-representation of zero-one linear programs for branch and cut, *ORSA Journal Computing*, 3, 121-134
- Lin, Y., Austin, L.M. & Burns, T.W. (1992). An intelligent algorithm for mixed integer programming models, *Comps & Opns Res*, 19, 461- 468.
- Lee, E.K. & Mitchell, J.E. (1997). Computational Experience of an Interior-point SQP algorithm in a parallel Branch and Bound Framework, Technical Report LEC 97-08, Industrial and Systems Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta.
- Murty, K. Djang, P. Butler, W. & Laferriere, R. (1995). The Army Training Mix Model. *Journal of Operations Research Society* 46, 298 – 303.
- Nemhauser, G.L.,(1996), "Applications of mixed-integer programming to problems of the U.S. Army" School of Industrial and Systems Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology 1996
- Ramirez-Baltran, N.D. (1995) . Integer programming to minimize labour costs. *Journal of Operations Research Society* 46, 139-146.
- Smith, J.O. (2005). Exponential decay. Technical Report, Centre for Computer Research in music and acoustics, Stanford University, notes
- Taha, H.A. (2003). Operations Research an Introduction, (7th edition) Prentice Hall, New Delhi.
- Yang, T., and Ignizio, J.P., (1987), "An algorithm for the scheduling of army battalion training exercises", *Comput. Opns Res.* Vol. 14, No. 6, pp. 479-491.